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CANGARDAK RIVER BASIN IS A PRECIOUS SOURCE OF RARE SPECIES

Khalmuratov M.A.

Candidate of Biological Sciences,
Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy.

Tashmirov S.E. Msc,

Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy.

ABSTRACT

The article includes information on the chemical composition and application of some rare and medicinal plant species distributed in the Sangardak River Basin and listed in the "Red Data Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords

The Sangardak River, Sicilian sumac, *Paeonia hybrida*, *Ungernia victoris*, *Scutellaria guttata*, giant onion, small-flowered locoweed, Sardinian currant, Griffith's redbud, the pasqueflowers, Sicilian sumac, milkvetch, desert candle.

The Sangardak River rises from the Hisar Ridge's southwest side as the right tributary of the Surkhan River (3800 m). The basin's length is 114 km and its area is 948 km². The average height is 2286 meters, and the catchment area is 889 km². It is called Degikanora in the upper stream (until it joins the Kyzilsoy). The mountains here are exceedingly steep, and the river is very narrow. Kyzilsoy (15 km), Shorchioy (11 km), and Molongur (23 km) are three tiny streams that enter the Sangardak river from the right side; Khandiza (25 km) and Nilu are two others that enter the Sangardak river from the left side (11 km). The Sangardak River mostly increases by seasonal snow and groundwater. The highest water usage is 44 m³/sec (in May), and 4.38–4.04 m³/sec from November to January.

The plants of the Sangardak river basin are distinguished by their distinctiveness, medicinal properties and other aspects. Since the beginning of time, people have used these plants for a variety of purposes, including food preparation, fabric dyeing, leather processing, and the treatment of numerous diseases. In our country, there are over 4,500 different plant species, and more than 600 of these are beneficial medicinal herbs. At present, their number is expanding.

More than half of the therapeutic compounds used in modern science medicine are derived from plants. As a result, humans need to adopt a new perspective on the world of plants and use them wisely while trying to preserve as many of their species and their roots as they can.

The scientific research was carried out in the mountainous area of the Sangardak river basin, where there are comparatively few broad-leaved trees and bushes. Thus, the following types of plants were discovered in the form of communities:

Shrub-tree-*Acer turkestanicum*s

- High spike grass-shrub-tree mixed-hairy-maples,
 - Shrubby-jashir-hairy-mixed woodlands
 - Mixed herbaceous-mugwort-maple mixed-shrub
- Mixed herbaceous - wheat-sparse tree mixed-shrub
- Mugwort- large grass They typically form communities in small places, mostly along the sides of streams, in the upper reaches of the Sangardak and Halkajar rivers, and in sparser juniper woods. They are found in the form of a mixed shrubland with wheat and other communities (see classification and map). Dzhangurazov's 1951 data states that 102 plants and shrubs were discovered among them. Hawthorn, almond, namatak species, three-leaf clover, shum, maple species, zirk, koshbarg, kirzhach, porsildak, irgay, chiya, and other species are among the most prevalent.

Some plant species found in the Sangardak river basin and included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan are thought to be significant in terms of their chemical makeup and uses. They include:

Sicilian sumac (*Rhus coriaria* L.). The leaf contains 10-20.9% tannin, up to 4.8% gallic acid and its esters, as well as flavonoids (avicularin, astragalin, myricitrin, etc.). Tannin is extracted from the leaf.

***Paeonia hybrida* Pall.** The plant contains up to 1.6% essential oil, salicin glycoside, up to 78.5% starch, up to 10% sugars, peonol (oxyphenylmethylketone), 1.66-2.6% iridoids, salicylic and benzoic acids, a small amount of saponins, alkaloids, additives and micro-elements.

In medicine, functional nervous system disorders, neurasthenia, and insomnia are treated with a sedative derived from the peony plant.

The central nervous system is calmed by a 10% infusion of peony roots and tops without affecting blood pressure or respiratory rate.

***Ungernia victoris* Vved. ex Artjuschenko.** The leaves of the plant contain 0.33-1%, the bulb contains 0.8-0.9%, and the root contains 1.8-2.55% of alkaloids.

From alkaloids, galantamine, lycorine, tatsetine, narvedine, gordine, pancratine and other alkaloids were isolated. Galantamine and lycorine alkaloids are obtained from the leaves of some species of *Ungernia*. The hydrobromide salt of Galantamine is used in the treatment of myosthenia (pathological muscle weakness or false paralysis), myopathy (shrinkage and gradual weakening of muscles), complications of poliomyelitis, and polyneuritis, radiculitis, as well as traumatic disruption of nerves, relaxation (weakening) of the intestine and bladder. The hydrochloride salt of lycorine is used as an expectorant in severe and chronic inflammation of the lungs and bronchi, and in the treatment of bronchial asthma and other diseases.

Scutellaria guttata Nevski ex Juz. The root and rhizome contain 4.5% (20 pieces) of flavonoids, the most important of which are baicalein (degraded to glucuronic acid and baicalein when dehydrogenated), scutellarin (degraded to scutellarein and glucuronic acid) and wogonin. In addition to flavonoids, the product contains tar, up to 2.5% pyrocatechin and essential oil. The flavonoid scutellarin was extracted from its stem and leaf.

Medicinal preparation of the plant is used as an antihypertensive and sedative agent in the treatment of various forms of hypertension, headache, insomnia, and nervous disorders.

Salvia insignis Kudr.) All parts of the plant contain essential oil. The leaves contain 0.5-2.5% essential oil, alkaloids, astringents, flavonoids, ursolic and oleanolic acids and other compounds. The essential oil contains up to 15% cineol, thuion, pinene, borneol, camphor, cedrene and other compounds. The preparations from its leaves are used as astringent, disinfectant and anti-inflammatory medicine for inflammation of the upper respiratory tract, mouthwash (stomatitis and gingivitis) and throat.

Milkvetch (genus *Astragalus*). The product contains glycyrrhizin and other triterpene glycosides, flavonoids and micro-elements. The medicinal preparation of the product from this plant is used in the treatment of diseases of the cardiovascular system, hypertension and nephritis.

Desert Candle (*Eremurus alberti Regel*). Due to the presence of a sticky substance (juice) in the roots of many species, it is used to obtain glue. Its leaves contain a lot of vitamin C and are a good honey plant.

Silene michelsonii Preobr. The plant contains polyisoprenoids (mixture of polyprenols) and α -tocopherols (vitamin E), ecdysteroids and iridoids. The plant is rich in ecdysteroids and has long been used in folk medicine to treat various diseases. Ecdysterone, polypodin B, turkesterone and integristerone A isolated from these plants are physiologically active compounds with a wide range of effects, which together with antioxidant, anabolic, hypoglycemic, hemorheological effects on the human body are

used for faster healing of wounds, myocarditis, atherosclerosis, anti-cancer, bone fracture and has a positive effect in the treatment of hepatitis.

The pasqueflowers or windflowers (genus *Anemone*). The leaves of representatives contain up to 30% protein and 270-350 mg/kg of carotene. They contain riboflavin, polyvitamins, ascorbic acid, K, E, D and other vitamins. The seed contains 18-20% protein, 8-9% oil and 65-75% carbohydrates. The oil has healing properties for stomach and intestinal ulcers, and is used to accelerate the healing of skin diseases and cut wounds.

Griffith's Redbud (*Cercis griffithii* Boiss.). The product contains vitamin K₁, ascorbic and panthenic acids, 2.5% oil, 0.12% essential oil, 2.7% resinous and up to 2.15% bitter substances, 3.18% saponin, inositol, 0.05% alkaloids and other compounds. Oil from the plant is used in the prevention and treatment of atherosclerosis. In addition, it reduces the amount of cholesterol in the blood and improves the metabolism of lipids in the body.

***Calophaca reticulata* Sumnev.** It contains 0.01-0.05% essential oil, 10-11% sugar, 10 mg % vitamin C, 60 mg % vitamin B₁, carotene, flavonoids (quercetin and its glycosides). The leaf contains 20 mg % vitamin C, 50 mg % vitamin B₂, 4 mg % carotene, essential oil, lemon and malic acid. Medicinal preparations of the plant are prescribed for the treatment of intestinal atony, colitis, arteriosclerosis, sclerotic form of hypertension and avitaminosis. These extractions are applied to the mucous membranes of the nose in case of rhinitis and are also used in the treatment of trichomonad colpitis in gynecology.

Sardinian currant (*Ribes malvifolium* Pojark). The leaf contains 0.25% ascorbic acid and essential oil. The fruit contains 0.4% ascorbic acid, 3 mg% carotene, vitamins B₁ and P, 2.5-4.5% organic acids, 4.5-16.8% sugar, 0.43% flavoring and up to 5% pectin substances, anthocyanin compounds and their glycosides as well as flavanoids.

Its leaves, fruits and preparations are used to treat scurvy and other hypo and avitaminosis diseases. The fruit is used in folk medicine as a diaphoretic and diuretic, anti-diarrhea, and the leaf is used as a diarrhoea.

Small-flowered locoweed (*Oxytropis tyttantha* Gontsch.) Flowers contain 0.2-0.66% essential oil, 5-6% flavoring and other substances and a large amount of potassium salts. It was found that sapofanin α -amyrin is an anglicon of one of the saponins.

The preparation of the plant is used as a diuretic in kidney disease (kidney stone disease) and cholecystitis, together with cardiac glycosides in P-Sh level diseases of the cardiovascular system.

***Salvia insignis* Kudr.** All parts of the plant contain essential oil. The leaf contains 0.5-

2.5% essential oil, alkaloids, flavoring substances, flavonoids, ursolic and oleanolic acids and other compounds.

Medicinal preparations from its leaves are used as an expectorant, disinfectant and anti-inflammatory drug for inflammation of the upper respiratory tract, for gargling the mouth (stomatitis and gingivitis) and throat.

Giant onion (*Allium giganteum* Regel). Bulbs contain 0.01-0.05% essential oil, 10-11% sugar, 10 mg % vitamin C, 60 mg % vitamin B₁, carotene, flavonoids (quercetin and its glycosides). The leaves of the plant contain 20 mg % vitamin C, 50 mg % vitamin B₂, 4 mg % carotene, essential oil, citric and malic acids. The essential oil from the bulbs contains sulfur compounds (mainly disulfide and others).

Medicinal extractions from this species are used to treat intestinal atony, colitis, arteriosclerosis as well as the sclerotic form of hypertension and avitaminosis. These extractions are applied to the mucous membranes of the nose in case of rhinitis and are also used in the treatment of trichomonad colpitis in gynecology. The extractions from the bulbs of plants have bactericidal properties. Mashed bulbs are also used to treat wounds that are difficult to heal and suppurating. In folk medicine, its bulbs are used as a diuretic and medicine for treating scurvy.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it can be said that the basin of the Sangardak River is distinguished by its abundance of plant species, which are the main ones in terms of rarity, importance and use.

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